

AI-assisted Hazard Detection for safe lunar landing

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Identifying hazards that could compromise a safe landing is a critical step of the final phases of a lander descent trajectory. Landing on a harsh terrain can lead to the lander tipping over or prevent a deployed payload from fulfilling its mission. Many attempts to develop Hazard Detection systems failed to provide a comprehensive and robust assessment of the hazards present in the landing area, particularly under adverse lighting conditions. The proposed algorithm utilizes deep learning techniques combined with standard processing methods to deliver a secure landing site to the onboard Guidance, Navigation, and Control system. By integrating data from optical images and LiDAR point clouds, the algorithm evaluates slope, extent, local roughness, presence of obstacles, and permanently shadowed regions, while also considering the fuel expenses required to reach the designated site. The deep learning algorithm's training and validation, as well as the hazard detection pipeline's testing, were conducted using synthetic images and point clouds generated from a virtual simulation environment created in Unreal Engine, which enabled varying lighting conditions and lander orientation and altitude. The algorithm has yielded satisfactory outcomes, effectively pinpointing a secure landing location across all conducted tests, thus reaffirming the validity of the approach.

1 Introduction

The exploration of the Moon, particularly its polar regions, has garnered significant scientific interest due to the potential presence of ice deposits, which hold promise for scientific research and resource harnessing. This renewed focus has driven international initiatives like Artemis [1] to establish lunar outposts and conduct extensive sampling missions, ultimately aimed at bringing men back to the Moon. Over the past decade, several missions have successfully landed on the lunar surface. Chang'e 5 landed on December 1, 2020, marking a recent successful lunar sample return mission [2]. Chandrayaan-3, launched on July 14, 2023, saw its Vikram lander touch down

on August 23, becoming the first spacecraft to land on the Moon's South Pole region [3]. However, numerous missions have also faced failures. Notably, on February 22, 2024, the Nova-C lander, Odysseus, developed by Intuitive Machines, successfully landed near the Malapert A crater in the Moon's South Pole region. Despite being designed to remain upright on slopes over 10°, it landed on a 12° slope, causing it to skid, damage one of its legs, and tip over [4, 5].

To mitigate the risks of encountering physical hazards during the final landing phases, active and passive sensors can be deployed for hazard detection purposes. Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) sensors provide detailed terrain mapping but are known for their high cost, power consumption, and bulkiness, while cameras, as passive sensors, offer valuable data in a more compact form but are susceptible to adverse lighting conditions. Despite their individual limitations, the combined use of LiDAR and cameras remains a viable and, in many cases, advantageous solution. Previous Hazard Detection and Avoidance (HDA) efforts, such as those in the Chang'e 3, 4, and 5 missions, utilized visual-based hazard detection systems that combined 2-D optical gray-image-based coarse hazard avoidance with 3-D laser-based methods [6–8]. These systems identified significant hazards like craters and large boulders from altitudes below 2 km down to approximately 100 m, determining the safest landing site. Similarly, the Mars 2020 Perseverance Rover's landing utilized Terrain Relative Navigation (TRN) technology, which processed camera imagery against an onboard map to detect obstacles [9]. Traditional processing techniques, although simple and fast, lack the adaptability required for accurate hazard detection. However, advancements in artificial intelligence for computer vision, geared towards onboard implementation, promise to enhance the flexibility, efficiency and effectiveness of HDA algorithms. The approach in [10] employs a Vision Transformer [11] model to extract terrain features from low-light RGB images for recognizing hazards such as craters.

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Although this model offers a low-power solution for adverse illumination conditions, it is not a viable alternative to active sensors. In [12], a U-Net [13] architecture is used to label image areas as safe or unsafe, identifying the safest spot as the pixel furthest from hazardous regions. Relying solely on a monocular camera makes this method sensitive to shadows, and its inherently 2-D input data may not enable accurate detection of surface slope and roughness. Another method, described in [14], uses a MobileNetV2 [15] to detect hazardous obstacles within a monocular image, which is then processed using a Structure from Motion (SfM) algorithm to derive slope and roughness information. This approach is highly sensitive to lighting conditions and requires multiple images from different viewpoints to accurately detect surface properties, which may not be feasible in a low-velocity hovering scenario. Conversely, [16] proposed a deep learning method using a U-Net-like architecture to analyze LiDAR scans and identify safe landing sites, with ground truth established starting from Digital Elevation Maps (DEMs) of the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO) mission. While robust to lighting conditions, this method cannot detect shadowed regions and smaller hazards such as rocks and boulders.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, none of the proposed systems are able to achieve effective and comprehensive detection of hazards while simultaneously maintaining robustness under unfavorable lighting conditions. Additionally, the detection of Permanently Shadowed Regions (PSRs), which represent undesirable landing locations due to their extremely low temperature, is often overlooked. In this paper, a novel hazard detection algorithm is proposed, which fuses data from an onboard LiDAR and a monocular camera. By combining deep learning and standard processing techniques, it aims to comprehensively and robustly assess hazard areas and ultimately provide the Guidance, Navigation and Control (GNC) system with a safe landing site. The subsequent sections of the manuscript are organized as follows: Section 2 provides a comprehensive overview of the proposed system architecture. Showcased in Section 2 is also a novel virtual lunar environment built in Unreal Engine 5 [17] exploited to generate synthetic images and point clouds. In Section 3, the outcomes of the algorithm are presented across a series of selected test cases. Finally, Section 4 provides a conclusive discussion on the achieved results.

2 Methodology

The proposed hazard detection algorithm exploits deep learning and standard processing techniques to

extract from optical images and LiDAR point clouds meaningful data about the terrain underneath the lander. Particularly, information about surface geometry is retrieved from the LiDAR. Conversely, an optical image acquired over the same region is employed to detect smaller obstacles, such as rocks, which the LiDAR may miss due to its lower spatial resolution. The pipeline targets the hovering phase, from 2 km to about 500 m of altitude. Both the camera and the LiDAR sensors are assumed to be pointing in the nadir direction, an assumption that is likely valid during the hovering phase. Due to the scarcity of high-resolution images of the Moon and LiDAR acquisitions at such close proximity to the lunar surface, a virtual landing scenario has been developed to generate synthetic lunar terrain data. This tool, built in the Unreal Engine 5 graphics engine, will be briefly described in the following Subsection.

2.1 Virtual Landing Scenario

Starting from the DEM generated by the LRO Lunar Orbiter Laser Altimeter (LOLA), a highly detailed 3D model of the lunar south pole terrain has been constructed. Subsequently, the surface model was imported into Unreal Engine 5, harnessing its capabilities to manage high-polygon meshes and create high-fidelity scenes. This was made possible through innovative technologies such as Nanite [18], Virtual Shadow Maps (VSMs) [19], and Lumen [20]. The scenario has been equipped with synthetic data generation capabilities, including the ability to produce LiDAR scans and high-resolution images with customizable lighting conditions and intrinsic sensor parameters. The images' high fidelity is also enabled by the selected surface material, which mimics the optical behavior of lunar regolith (Figure 1). Furthermore, the tool features the possibility of randomly placing rocks over the lunar surface tiles, enhancing the terrain fidelity with additional surface details. Finally, the tool enables the generation of segmented datasets, streamlining the process of training neural networks (Figure 1(d)).

2.2 Hazard Detection Algorithm

The Hazard Detection algorithm unfolds across 5 main stages. Initially, the raw point cloud is processed and projected onto a plane perpendicular to the sensor boresight direction, yielding a map of local terrain elevations. Subsequently, a slope map is generated by computing the gradient of the elevation map, providing the maximum terrain slope for each pixel. Next, an initial hazard map is created, excluding all regions with a slope greater than a user-selectable threshold.

Figure 1: Examples of generated synthetic data. (a) depicts a lunar surface tile generated within the virtual scenario. (b) present an example of a synthetic LiDAR acquisition. Examples of random rocks placement and automatic segmented dataset generation are depicted in (c) and (d), respectively.

Figure 2: Example of obstacle detection performed by the YOLOv5s detector with a confidence threshold of 0.30. The image has been captured at an altitude of 500 m, with the smallest detected object exhibiting about 1 m in diameter.

Subsequently, using position information from the autonomous navigation module and a database of PSRs stored onboard [21], zones included in PSRs are also labelled as hazardous. A first region proposal algorithm identifies 8-connected regions within the map. Then, a second stage region proposal procedure fits circles within each region, ensuring that the diameters exceed a predefined threshold. Overlapping circles are merged into a single region, whose boundary is smoothed by computing its convex hull. Concomitantly, a YOLOv5s model [22], trained on a dataset of synthetic images obtained from the virtual environment (Section 2.1), detects smaller hazard sources (such as rocks and boulders) within the optical image. Each region identified by the region proposal procedure is assigned a score based on the average slope,

surface extent, roughness (computed as the standard deviation of local terrain height) and the number of small obstacles detected by the neural network within the area. Additionally, the distance from the originally programmed landing site also contributes to determining the score of each region, thus preventing overly abrupt maneuvers and limiting the use of propellant. Finally, the safe landing site is selected as the region that minimizes the following cost function:

$$J(\mathcal{R}_k) = - \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i \log \left(\frac{p_i(\mathcal{R}_k)}{P_i} \right), \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{R}_k denotes the k -th region, $p_i(\mathcal{R}_k)$ indicates the i -th parameter evaluated for region \mathcal{R}_k and N the number of parameters that contribute to the region score. P_i represents a scale factor for the i -th parameter. For example, in the case of the overall extent of the region, the scale factor corresponds to the entire area of the framed surface. Finally, α_i denotes a weight attributed to each parameter, representing the importance of said parameter in contributing to the overall region score.

3 Results

The YOLOv5s obstacle detector was trained on a dataset comprising over 2000 synthetic images derived from the virtual scenario described in Section 2.1. The pictures dataset has been augmented by randomly varying the Sun azimuth angle between 0° and 360° , the Sun elevation between 5° and 15° , and by varying the camera orientation and distance from the terrain. The detector exhibited a remarkable $mAP_{0.50}$ of 0.61. Figure 2 shows an example of obstacle detection on a synthetic image not included in the training and validation datasets. The training parameters for the YOLOv5s network are reported in Table 1. The YOLOv5s model was preferred over larger YOLOv5 models due to its lightweight nature, which

Figure 3: Tests conducted on the proposed Hazard Detection algorithm. Detailed discussion of the test cases is presented in Section 3. The blue dot represent the initially programmed landing spot. Depicted in green are the boundaries of the computed safe landing area, whose centroid is represented with a red dot. Bounding boxes for the YOLOv5-based obstacle detector are also shown. Yellow curves depict PSRs.

Training Parameters	
Learning Rate	0.01
Optimizer	Stochastic Gradient Descent
Momentum	0.937
Weight Decay	0.0005
N. of Epochs	300
Image Size	512
Batch Size	32

Table 1: Training parameters used for training the YOLOv5s lunar rocks detector on the synthetic dataset generated within the Virtual Landing Scenario introduced in Section 2.1.

strikes a favorable balance between complexity and inference speed, considering the limited computational capabilities available onboard.

The complete hazard detection pipeline underwent testing across four distinct test cases, which were constructed by varying the landing area, lighting conditions, and altitude. In all scenarios, a monocular camera with a resolution of 1024x1024 pixels and a Field of View (FOV) of 90° was employed. The LiDAR system’s pixel grid has been set to 512x512, with the same FOV as the camera. Each weight α_i in Equa-

tion (1) has been set to 1. For each test, the maximum acceptable slope was set to 5° and the previously designed landing spot has been assumed to be at the center of the frame. All test cases are showcased in Figure 3. Test case (a) was conducted on a flat area with large craters at the edges, at an altitude of 2 km. No small obstacles were visible. The safe landing zone identified by the algorithm, shown in Figure 3(a), has successfully avoided craters and high-slope zones. In test case (b), the algorithm’s performance was evaluated in a crater-rich area at 1.5 km altitude. Due to the surface roughness and the presence of obstacles detected by the YOLOv5s obstacle detector, the algorithm opted for a peripheral landing site. Test case (c) involved an area with steep slope variations caused by the presence of a large crater in the northwest part of the region. Although the crater floor was initially identified as flat by the algorithm, this area was excluded from the safe regions due to the presence of a PSR within it, highlighted in Figure 3(c). Finally, in test case (d), the pipeline’s behavior was analyzed in a scenario closer to the ground, at 500 m altitude, with relatively larger obstacles. In this case, all regions of interest exhibited similar surface properties, therefore the algorithm opted for an area free of rocks that was sufficiently close to the previously programmed landing site.

4 Discussion

The proposed hazard detection algorithm merges the simplicity, speed, and robustness of traditional processing methods with the power and adaptability of deep learning techniques to provide a comprehensive assessment of dangers the lander may encounter during the terminal hovering phase. Small and medium-sized obstacles are detected using a YOLOv5s network, trained on a fully synthetic dataset. Concomitantly, LiDAR acquisitions are processed to retrieve additional information on surface roughness and slope. Each proposed safe region is assigned a score based on a comprehensive set of safety parameters, including the possible presence of PSRs and fuel consumption required to reach it. The algorithm underwent testing in varying lighting conditions, surface geometry, altitude and obstacle distribution. The pipeline yielded satisfactory results, demonstrating its ability to appropriately weigh scoring parameters and select the safest landing site. Looking ahead, future work will involve testing the inference times of the network and the overall algorithm computation on dedicated hardware to evaluate the feasibility of onboard implementation. Moreover, interest in event-based landing is increasing due to event cameras being lightweight, highly responsive, and having a high dynamic range, in contrast to LiDARs, which are bulky and heavy. The presented simulator could be expanded with the capability to generate event-based data, providing the opportunity to investigate the integration of such data into the hazard detection pipeline.

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